

Low-speed scalar control of induction motor by fuzzy logic

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ABSTRACT

Efforts have continually been directed toward optimizing processes in various fields, and the application in induction motors is no exception. Scalar control V/f offers a straightforward method to regulate the speed of a three-phase induction motor (TIM). However, it faces challenges at low speeds or proportionally at low frequencies, often failing to operate below 20% of its rated speed. This control typically pairs with a PI controller (PIC) for closed-loop speed regulation, but its limited control range hinders performance at low speeds. Although intelligent methods have been developed to improve scalar V/f control, attention is often focused on high speeds, while control at low speeds is overlooked. This paper presents the simulation of a fuzzy controller (FC) with a Mamdani-type structure designed to achieve effective low-speed control of a TIM using the V/f scalar control technique. The results not only show improvements in overshoot and settling time but also reveal that the FC can control speeds as low as 6.06% of the rated speed, and it ensures a starting current below the designed motor current under load. Comparative analysis indicates that the FC outperforms the PIC in low-speed control, and it provides an optimal inrush current across different low speeds.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The use of direct current (DC) motors has declined in various applications, including electric and hybrid vehicles and railway systems [1], [2]. As a result, the three-phase induction motor (TIM) has been preferred over DC motors due to its ease of maintenance, high reliability, cost-effectiveness, simple design, robust durability, and excellent power-to-weight ratio [3]. Consequently, there has been growing interest in advanced control techniques, primarily V/f scalar control and vector control.

It is noted that V/f scalar control is chosen for its simplicity, practicality, and cost-effectiveness [4], although it struggles at low speeds—typically below 20% of the motor's nominal speed—because the flux increases significantly, leading to torque and current surges [5], [6]. Additionally, it is acknowledged that starting currents in TIM can reach up to ten times the rated current [4], [7], [8], increasing risks to electrical components, potentially overloading power systems, and resulting in economic drawbacks [9]. Hence, it is emphasized that methods aimed at achieving an optimal peak starting current and a suitable speed response, especially at low frequencies, are essential for improved motor performance.

PI controllers (PICs) have been frequently employed in V/f scalar control for speed regulation in TIMs [10], [11], and are reported to be suitable in contexts where a detailed mathematical model is difficult to establish due to resource constraints and complex operations [8], [12]. Their capacity to minimize or eliminate steady-state errors, combined with a simple structure, has been emphasized [13], although their performance is limited in speed response and under load variations [14]. These drawbacks have led to efforts to improve PIC through enhanced techniques [15], [16], yet difficulties remain at low speeds, especially concerning speed response and inrush current management. Consequently, fuzzy logic control has been examined in V/f scalar control for TIMs [17], [18], where it has been recognized for its accuracy and robustness [19]. However, although improvements in transient behavior (overshoot, settling time, and rise time) have been identified, the advantages of fuzzy controllers (FC) at low speeds have received limited attention, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Approaches of fuzzy and V/f scalar control in TIMs

Type of analysis	Advantages	Disadvantages
Integration of fuzzy logic with variable frequency drive [20].	Improved energy efficiency, real-time speed adjustment, and reliability and economically beneficial.	High initial costs, dependency on specialized hardware that can lead to accessibility problems.
Development of an optimal fuzzy-PIC [21].	Reduced computational load, improved speed response, reduced rule set, and faster stabilization.	Limited to a specific rpm range (1300-1725 rpm).
Fuzzy logic controllers for speed control under fluctuating loads [22].	Faster adjustment to speed changes, robustness against load disturbances, and simplifies control schemes.	Focus on high speeds (specifically 1000 rpm), potentially limited lower speed performance.

It is noted that modifying the V/f scalar control can compensate for torque at low frequencies, based on a “Torque boost” approach [23]. Increasing electrical starting torque is essential to overcome mechanical torque, although it induces higher inrush currents, which are a key consideration for motor startup [24]. The equations in [25] show that the starting torque depends on the inrush current.

The possibility of a fuzzy logic-based torque compensation at low frequencies, termed “Current compensation”, is considered to achieve a “Torque boost” for TIMs under V/f scalar control. This raises the question of whether such fuzzy logic controller (FLC) can deliver an effective speed response and optimize inrush current below 20% of the rated speed, while retaining the improvements offered by the FC in transient response. Hence, this work aims to enhance the PIC for V/f speed regulation by coupling a PIC with an FLC method. The objective is to optimize low-speed control response, manage inrush current, and enlarge the operational control range [5], [26]. Explicit criteria for speed and current in transient scenarios are established to enable a parameter comparison between the FC and the PIC, conveying mathematical objectivity.

2. METHOD

This research involves the development, simulation, and evaluation of a fuzzy-logic-enhanced V/f scalar control scheme for a TIM, leveraging MATLAB/Simulink and Lucas–Nuelle’s toolbox. The objective is to provide an AI-based solution to the challenges of scalar V/f control at low speeds. First, the V/f scalar control system was designed; next, negative feedback was implemented using a PIC tuned via particle swarm optimization (PSO). The PIC-based feedback loop was then analyzed to develop a FC-based feedback loop within the scalar V/f framework. Finally, both the PIC and FC schemes were simulated, evaluated, and compared in terms of speed and current responses over a predefined speed range, with particular emphasis on low-speed performance. Figure 1 shows the overall block diagram of the low-speed scalar V/f control system with the FC, detailing the key components and their interactions to provide a complete overview of the system’s functionality.

2.1. V/f scalar control design

2.1.1. V/f relation

Before establishing the V/f relationship, a scaling factor of 1/30 is introduced so that the synchronous speed, n_s , can be handled conveniently in revolutions per minute (rpm). This conversion appears in (1), which is derived from the fundamental synchronous-speed expression shown in (2). In both equations, f denotes the supply frequency (Hz) and P represents the number of motor poles.

$$f = n_s \frac{1}{30} \quad (1)$$

$$n_s = \frac{120f}{P} \tag{2}$$

Under the assumed linear V/f profile, the stator frequency is limited to the 3 Hz–29 Hz interval, which corresponds to a controllable speed range of 100 rpm–800 rpm. An additional tolerance band is specified, narrowing the effective closed-loop range to 90 rpm–870 rpm to ensure reliable operation near the extreme points. Within this band, the modulation signal sent to the insulated gate bipolar transistor (IGBT) control block varies from 5% to 58% of the preset 220 V DC link voltage, since the voltage is normalized to frequency. Consequently, the resulting V/f characteristic is defined by (3), where $V_{V/f}$ is the output voltage determined by the V/f ratio; f is the reference frequency (Hz); A is the reference value corresponding to 100% of the DC link voltage; and f_{max} is the maximum (normalized) frequency for the V/f ratio.

$$V_{V/f} = \begin{cases} 0, & f < 0 \\ \frac{fA}{f_{max}}, & 0 \leq f \leq 50 \\ 100, & f > 50 \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

Figure 1. Fuzzy control block diagram

2.1.2. Clark-Park transformation

The Clarke–Park transformation is used to obtain three balanced sinusoidal references required by the inverter’s modulation stage. To generate the pulse-width modulation (PWM) signals for the inverter implemented with the LN blocks, the IGBT control block must receive three-phase sinusoidal signals that encode both the desired fraction of the preset DC link voltage and the switching frequency demanded by the IGBTs. These requirements are met by first applying the inverse Park transformation to the voltage reference obtained from the V/f ratio. The matrix form of the inverse Park transformation is given in (4).

$$\begin{bmatrix} D_s \\ Q_s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\theta) \\ \sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} V_\alpha \\ V_\beta \end{bmatrix} \tag{4}$$

Here, V_α is set to zero, and V_β , which stems from the V/f profile, is generated by an LN integrator block that resets every 2π with a period of $1/f$. Once the D_s and Q_s components are obtained, a modified inverse Clarke transformation, expressed in (5), is applied to translate these orthogonal voltages into the three-phase references required by the IGBT switches. In (5), U_c , V_c , and W_c constitute the final control signals delivered to the IGBT control block. Each signal simultaneously encodes, in its amplitude, the percentage of the inverter’s DC link voltage and, in its frequency, the carrier needed for accurate PWM generation.

$$\begin{bmatrix} U_c \\ V_c \\ W_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 \\ -\frac{1}{2} & \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & 1 \\ -\frac{1}{2} & -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} D_s \\ Q_s \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{5}$$

2.1.3. Three-phase inverter

The three-phase inverter, or simulation converter block, synthesizes the motor phase voltages by switching its insulated-gate bipolar transistors in response to the reference signals. These reference signals are

the standard IGBT control waveforms generated by the IGBT control block with PWM at 8 kHz. During each carrier period, the simulation converter block combines the IGBT control signals, the maximum PWM counter value, and the preset DC-link voltage to compute the instantaneous output voltages delivered to the motor [27]. Here, V_{dc} is supplied by a full-wave rectifier connected to the three-phase mains.

2.1.4. Three-phase induction motor model

The dynamic behavior of the drive is represented through a detailed TIM model. Figure 2 shows the single-phase equivalent circuit that underpins this model. Because the three stator phases are identical and the supply is perfectly balanced, the model derived from one phase can be extrapolated to the full machine. Accordingly, the three-phase induction motor model block, or induction model block, from the Lucas–Nülle toolbox implements the motor dynamics by numerically solving the fundamental equations listed in (6) to (8).

Figure 2. Induction motor monophasic equivalent circuit

In (6) expresses the mechanical torque M_{mech} as the ratio between electromagnetic power and rotor speed, whereas in (7) links the electromagnetic torque M and the load torque M_L to the rotor's angular acceleration through its moment of inertia J . In (8) provides a state-space description that simultaneously governs the stator currents (i_{sa} , i_{sb} , and rotor flux linkages (Ψ_{Ra} , Ψ_{Rb}) in the stationary $\alpha - \beta$ frame, using machine parameters such as L_s , L_r , L_m , R_s , R_r , and the time constants T_σ and T_R . Together, these equations capture the electromechanical coupling that defines induction-motor operation.

$$M_{mech} = \frac{P_{mech}}{\omega_m} = \frac{3}{2} z_p \frac{L_m}{L_R} (\Psi_{Ra} i_{sb} - \Psi_{Rb} i_{sa}) \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{J d\omega_m}{dt} = M - M_L \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{bmatrix} i_{sa}(t) \\ i_{sb}(t) \\ \Psi_{Ra}(t) \\ \Psi_{Rb}(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{1}{T_\sigma} & \omega_k & \frac{L_m}{\sigma L_S L_R T_R} & \frac{L_m}{\sigma L_S L_R} z_p \omega_m \\ -\omega_k & -\frac{1}{T_\sigma} & -\frac{L_m}{\sigma L_S L_R} z_p \omega_m & \frac{L_m}{\sigma L_S L_R T_R} \\ \frac{L_m}{T_R} & 0 & -\frac{1}{T_R} & (\omega_k - z_p \omega_m) \\ 0 & \frac{L_m}{T_R} & -(\omega_k - z_p \omega_m) & -\frac{1}{T_R} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{u}(t) \\ i_{sa}(t) \\ i_{sb}(t) \\ \Psi_{Ra}(t) \\ \Psi_{Rb}(t) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sigma L_S} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\sigma L_S} \\ 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} u_{sa}(t) \\ u_{sb}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

The symbols appearing in (6) to (8) are defined as follows:

- $i_{sa}(t)$, $i_{sb}(t)$ stator current components in the a and b axes at time t (A).
- $\Psi_{Ra}(t)$, $\Psi_{Rb}(t)$ rotor flux linkage components in the a and b axes at time t (Wb).
- ω_k , ω_m angular velocities: transformation and rotor (rad/s).
- T_σ , T_R constants: related to leakage and rotor.
- L_m , L_S , L_R inductances: magnetizing, stator, and rotor (H).
- z_p number of pole pairs.
- $u_{sa}(t)$, $u_{sb}(t)$ stator voltage components in the a and b axes at time t (V).
- M_{mech} , M , M_L torques: mechanical, electromagnetic and load (Nm).
- J - inertia moment of the rotor ($\text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2$).
- σ - total leakage coefficient.

To validate the control strategy, the Lucas–Nülle induction motor “SE2673-1K6” was selected. Its nameplate data are 220/380 V, 1.9/1.1 A, 60 Hz, 0.37 kW, 1650 rpm, and power factor of 0.76. The electrical and mechanical parameters used in the model are listed in Table 2. Employing manufacturer-specified values within the induction model block enhances the realism of the simulation and strengthens the correlation between numerical and experimental results.

Table 2. Lucas-Nuelle SE2673-1K6 electrical and mechanical parameters

Symbol	Description	Units	Value
L_r	Rotor inductance (related to the stator).	H	1.3867
L_s	Stator inductance.	H	1.3867
R_r	Rotor resistance.	Ω	15.72
R_s	Stator resistance	Ω	20.46
L_m	Magnetizing inductance	H	1.3
Inertia	Machine inertia	Kg m^2	0.0015
Friction	The friction moment, which depends on the rotating speed	μ	117e
z_p	Machine pole number		4

2.2. PI control design

For PIC design, an operational speed range of 100–800 rpm is adopted, with the midpoint of 450 rpm chosen as the nominal operating condition. The controller gains are tuned by a PSO algorithm, which searches the parameter space to obtain a set of constants that minimize the defined cost function. The resulting PIC is implemented in a cascade configuration, as illustrated in Figure 3, where $r(k)$ denotes the reference input, $y(k)$ the measured speed output, $e(k)$ the error, $u(k)$ the control signal, and $u^{\text{sat}}(k)$ the saturated control signal applied to the plant. The saturation limits A and B and the sampling period T_s are explicitly shown to prevent windup [28]–[31], instability, and overcurrent conditions [32].

Figure 4 shows the closed-loop block diagram used to tune K_p and K_i on the MATLAB/Simulink platform. The PSO algorithm is coded in M-script and interacts with Simulink through iterative simulations. Its velocity and position updates in (10) and (11), respectively, and the fitness function minimizes the absolute speed error.

$$\vec{v}_i(t + 1) = \omega \vec{v}_i(t) + c_1 r_1 (\vec{p}_i(t) - \vec{x}_i(t)) + c_2 r_2 (\vec{g}(t) - \vec{x}_i(t)) \tag{10}$$

$$\vec{x}_i(t + 1) = \vec{x}_i(t) + \vec{v}_i(t + 1) \tag{11}$$

Figure 3. Cascade structure of a discrete PIC with anti-windup

Figure 4. Closed-loop block diagram of V/f scalar of speed control

The swarm is configured with 15 particles, a maximum of 20 iterations, acceleration coefficients $c_1=c_2=2$, and an inertial factor that decreases linearly from $\omega_{\text{max}}=1$ to $\omega_{\text{min}}=0.1$. Random numbers r_1 and r_2 are uniformly drawn from $[0,1]$ at every iteration to maintain search diversity. Under these settings, the algorithm returns $K_p=0.6834$ and $K_i=0.7890$ at the 450 rpm operating point; a subsequent fine adjustment yields final values of $K_p=0.671$ and $K_i=0.750$. After optimization, the PSO and Abs() blocks in

Figure 4 are removed, and the tuned Kp and Ki constants are hard-coded into the PIC, completing the controller-design procedure.

2.3. Fuzzy control design

For FC design, the PIC is first evaluated over the 100–800 rpm operating range, selecting several midpoints tuned with the PSO procedure. The resulting data provide expert-level knowledge that is encoded into fuzzy rules aimed at improving speed regulation performance with fuzzy logic. Design requirements are set to limit the inrush current peak to 1.52 A ($\approx 80\%$ of the rated current), confine the steady-state speed error to ± 5 rpm, achieve a settling time below 1 s, and restrict both overshoot and undershoot to 15%.

Figure 5 provides an overview of the fuzzy-controller membership functions. The FC combines a Mamdani-type FLC with a conventional PIC whose gains Kp and Ki are adaptively selected by the FLC. The universe of discourse spans 100–800 rpm. The two inputs—reference speed and speed error—are mapped to triangular membership functions, while the two outputs—Kp and Ki—are likewise represented by triangular sets. As shown in Figure 5(a), speed is classified as low (LV), medium (MV), or high (HV); the velocity-error sets are small (SE), medium (ME), and large (LE). Figure 5(b) displays the output sets: small (SP), medium (MP), and large (LP) for Kp; and small (SI), medium (MI), and large (LI) for Ki. The rule base, summarized in Table 3, comprises nine “if-then” rules that use an AND conjunction, the minimum operator for implication, and the maximum operator for aggregation. Following aggregation, the centroid method is applied for defuzzification, yielding crisp values of Kp and Ki that satisfy the aforementioned performance criteria.

Both the FLC and the discrete PI control law are implemented in a MATLAB function block within the MATLAB/Simulink environment. The PI equation is coded in difference form, and an anti-windup limiter—implemented by saturating the control variable between $\pm A$ and $\pm B$ —prevents windup, instability, and overcurrent. Figure 1 presents the complete closed-loop diagram of the system governed by the FC.

Figure 5. Fuzzy controller membership functions: (a) input and (b) output

Table 3. Fuzzy controller rules

V _e	SE	ME	LE
LV	LP/LI	MP/MI	SP/SI
MV	MP/MI	MP/MI	SP/SI
HV	SP/SI	MP/MI	SP/SI

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Closed-loop responses of the V/f scalar control scheme were evaluated at reference speeds of 100, 250, 400, 575, and 750 rpm under load torques of 0.19, 0.24, and 0.41 Nm. Both the PIC and the FC were tested to enable a direct comparison. Figures 6 to 8 show dynamic behavior for three representative operating points. Figure 6(a) displays the speed response; Figure 6(b) the inrush current; and Figure 6(c) the permanent current—all at 100 rpm with a 0.19 Nm load. Similarly, Figure 7 presents the same responses at a 250 rpm reference with a 0.24 Nm load, while Figure 8 shows the same responses at a 100 rpm reference with a 0.21 Nm load.

Tables 4 and 5 list the principal response indices—undershoot, undershoot time, settling time, inrush-current RMS, and permanent-current RMS—across the five reference speeds noted above under the specified load levels. Table 6 condenses these data into performance differentials between the two controllers, while Table 7 summarizes the transient parameters and their variation in the low-speed robustness test conducted at 100 rpm and 0.21 Nm, based on the dynamic behavior shown in Figure 8. The robustness scenarios depicted

in Figure 8 and Table 7 deliberately exceed the original design constraints and illustrate each controller's behavior under demanding conditions.

Figure 6. The first and second columns present the PIC and FC responses respectively at 100 rpm and 0.19 Nm: (a) speed, (b) start-up current, and (c) steady-state current

Figure 7. The first and second columns present the PIC and FC responses respectively at 250 rpm and 0.24 Nm: (a) speed, (b) start-up current, and (c) steady-state current

Figure 8. The speed robustness test at low speed (100 rpm and 0.21 Nm): (a) speed, (b) start-up current, and (c) steady-state current

Table 4. Speed and current response parameters at 100, 250, and 400 rpm

Parameter	PIC		FC		PIC		FC	
Reference velocity [rpm]	100		250		400			
Load [Nm]	0.19		0.24		0.41			
Undershoot [%]	57.52	13.85	15.50	14.20	11.92	11.12		
Undershoot time [s]	0.08	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.03		
Setting time [s]	1.92	0.39	0.38	0.31	0.85	0.72		
Inrush current RMS [mA]	541.01	1490.58	861.96	912.87	1286.23	1335.02		
Permanent current RMS [mA]	443.00	443.14	528.00	528.21	623.67	623.46		

Table 5. Speed and current response parameters at 575 and 750 rpm

Parameter	PIC		FC	
Reference velocity [rpm]	575		750	
Load [Nm]	0.41		0.41	
Undershoot [%]	6.36	6.93	4.80	6.59
Undershoot time [s]	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03
Setting time [s]	0.43	0.29	2.33	0.43
Inrush current RMS [mA]	1668.77	1459.47	1999	1377.444
Permanent current RMS [mA]	634.77	626.921	656.9	659.5892

Table 6. Parameters comparison between controllers

Parameter	Controllers variations				
Reference velocity [rpm]	100	250	400	575	750
Load [Nm]	0.19	0.24	0.41	0.41	0.41
Undershoot [%]	43.67	1.3	0.8	-0.57	-1.79
Undershoot time [s]	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.01
Setting time [s]	1.53	0.07	0.13	0.14	1.90
Inrush current RMS [mA]	-949.57	-50.91	-48.79	209.30	621.55
Permanent current RMS [mA]	-0.14	-0.21	0.21	7.85	-2.69

Table 7. Robustness test parameters at low speeds

Parameter/Controller	PIC	FC	Variation
Reference velocity [rpm]		100	
Load [Nm]		0.21	
Undershoot [%]	undetermined	15.81	Not comparable
Undershoot time [s]	undetermined	0.02	Not comparable
Setting time [s]	Not stable	0.61	Not comparable
Inrush current RMS [mA]	657.26	1508.26	-851.00
Permanent current RMS [mA]	674.44	450.99	223.45

A comparative analysis between the FC and the PIC under identical design constraints confirms the FC's superior transient performance and robustness. Across the full speed span—from 100 to 800 rpm—the FC shortens settling time by up to 1.53 s at 100 rpm and by 1.90 s at 750 rpm, while keeping the steady-state speed within ± 5 rpm (Figures 6 and 7; Tables 4 to 6). These findings align with earlier studies showing that FC enhances the dynamic response of induction motor drives at medium, rated, and above-rated speeds [20]–[22], while the present work extends this evidence by validating a conventional PI-based scalar V/f control scheme at very low speeds.

Start-up current offers another clear distinction. Throughout the entire test range, the FC keeps the inrush current below the 1.52 A design ceiling as can be seen in Figures 6(b) and 7(b)—even though torque boost raises current demand at low speeds—whereas the PIC approaches or surpasses that threshold at several points. At 100 rpm, the torque-boost action eliminates the overshoot (23.2%) and reduces the extreme undershoot (57.52%) recorded with the PIC (Figure 6 and Table 4). This prevents the two-second stabilization delay that renders the PIC response unacceptable. Adaptive fuzzy schemes have demonstrated reductions in overshoot and stabilization time [21]; however, the improvements in low-speed control observed in this work exceed those of previous studies.

Although the FC occasionally registers undershoot values marginally higher than those of the PIC ($\leq 1.79\%$), these excursions remain well within the design limit, whereas the PIC violates it at 100 rpm (57.52%) and 250 rpm (15.50%) represented in Figures 6(a) and 7(a). Such undershoot magnitudes undermine optimal control performance. Moreover, across the evaluated range, the PIC exhibits the highest peak undershoot time—four times that of the FC. Hence, both techniques maintain adequate steady-state current behavior without producing side effects during continuous operation, see Figure 6(c) and 7(c).

The low-speed robustness test at 100 rpm and 0.21 Nm (Figure 8 and Table 7) exposes a critical difference in the same parameters analyzed above for the two control strategies. Although the PIC shows apparently adequate current waveforms—both during start-up and in steady state as shown in Figure 8(b) and Figure 8(c) it drives the speed response into an unrecoverable collapse, indicating an insufficient stability margin under even modest load disturbances, which is observed in Figure 8(a). By contrast, the FC maintains a peak-undershoot time comparable to the other speed cases, keeps the inrush current below the 1.52 A design limit, and achieves a stabilization pattern that mirrors the speed robustness reported for fuzzy schemes in previous studies [22], thereby demonstrating an acceptable level of robustness at low speed.

As a result, within a robustness margin of 0.21 Nm, the PIC must be ruled out, whereas the FC delivers a tolerable response; its only deviation from the specifications is an undershoot that exceeds the target by just 0.81%. This minor deviation could be eliminated by fine-tuning the fuzzy rule set or adjusting the membership-function boundaries. Overall, this comparison confirms that the FC retains acceptable robustness across the entire speed range, while the PIC's performance deteriorates sharply as operating conditions deviate from those analyzed.

To extend the discussion beyond the transient responses and robustness test, Figure 9 examines a ± 50 rpm speed-tracking test at 100 rpm under a 0.19 Nm load, where Figure 9(a) shows the speed dynamic response. Relative to the PIC, the FC reduces start-up overshoot and undershoot by 83.66% and 76%, respectively, and shortens the settling time by 0.831 s for the upward step and 0.719 s for the downward step. The FC also confines the overshoot and undershoot duration to only 26 ms—an order of magnitude faster than the PIC—thereby sustaining tight speed regulation even during rapid set-point changes. On the other hand, Figure 9(b) examines the transient behavior of the current, where the FC's starting current reaches at most 1.49 A. Despite the repetitive speed changes, the FC current maintains the same performance improvements. This result corroborates the scope of the FC's robustness and transient responses observed at low speed and mirrors the fast-adaptation behavior reported for fuzzy schemes at higher speeds in previous studies, while also demonstrating the enhanced starting performance achieved in this research—further highlighting the FC's superior agility, stability, and overall performance compared with the PIC.

Figure 9. The first and second columns present the PIC and FC responses, respectively, in the low-speed variation test at 100 rpm and 0.19 Nm: (a) speed and (b) current

4. CONCLUSION

This work presented a comparative analysis between PIC and FC in V/f scalar speed control of a TIM at low speeds, supported by simulations conducted in MATLAB/Simulink using Lucas-Nülle's toolbox for precise modeling. The results confirm that the integration of fuzzy logic significantly enhances speed regulation not only at low speeds but also across medium ranges, yielding superior dynamic performance. The FC achieved zero overshoot within a ± 2.9 rpm stability margin, reduced stabilization time by up to 0.29 s under different load conditions, and limited the starting current to below 76.8% of the motor's rated value, ensuring efficient control across the low-frequency region. Compared with the PIC, the FC consistently delivered better speed tracking and inrush-current mitigation, enabling operation at just 6.06% of rated speed while maintaining favorable transient characteristics under load. Future efforts will focus on implementing these control strategies in a physical setup to validate the simulation results under real operating scenarios, as well as refining the fuzzy rule base and membership functions to further enhance robustness and overall efficiency.

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Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The authors confirm that the data supporting the findings of this study are available within the article.

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